

Enhancing Self-Care of Nurses: A Healthy Nurse, Healthy Nation™ Project

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Background

Nurses were found to be unhealthier than the average American in several key domains:

- High-stress work environments
- Failure to meet self-care recommendations detailed by medical research

Several barriers to nurse self-care noted in the literature:

- Lack of institutional training
- Personal & environmental factors

Purpose

To address barriers to initiating and sustaining self-care behaviors specific to physical activity as identified by Healthy Nurse, Healthy Nation (HNN)

Aims

Describe personal and environmental factors experienced by nurses that may inhibit or enhance self-care behaviors

Develop educational materials and activities focused on increasing physical activity sustainability to contribute to HNN

Methods

Design: Cross-sectional design with development of evidence-based educational content

Setting: American Holistic Nurses Association (AHNA) partnership with HNN (national initiative that includes multiple locations)

Sample: Nurses ($n=15,492$) – Data period: February 2, 2017 to May 8, 2019

Measures: Health Risk Appraisal Survey (4 demographic, 10 multiple-choice, 1 close-ended, and 5 Likert scale items)

Framework: Modified Social Cognitive Theory

Results

Total Sample Nurse Minutes per Workout

Correlation (r) of Survey Items to Workouts per Week

Survey item	Light to Moderate	Vigorous	Muscle Strengthening
Mental/Physical Health issues	-.143*	-.113*	-.093*
Pain	-.117*	-.119*	-.076*
Stress at work	-.094*	-.054*	-.070*
Wellness Training in past 2 years	.097*	.058*	.054*
Emotional Support	.134*	.096*	.106*
Access to work wellness programs	.086*	.069*	.057*

* $p < .001$

Discussion

U.S. Department of Health and Human Services recommendations for physical activity

- 2.5 hours of moderate/vigorous exercise per week
- Muscle strengthening exercise 2 times per week

APRNs showed higher levels of physical activity than RNs and LVNs

Black/African American & middle-aged nurses showed lowest physical activity levels

Major barriers to physical activity

- Poor physical/mental health
- Pain

Significant correlations to increased physical activity

- Wellness training
- Emotional support

Future Implications

Healthcare and professional nursing organizations may benefit from providing opportunities for nurses to explore their current self-care status and work towards their future goals

Offering continuous educational and motivational wellness training activities can help nurses to sustain optimal physical activity levels

Start your self-care journey today at www.hnn.org !

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